

On the abundance of *Triturus ivanbureschi* Arntzen & Wielstra, 2013 (Amphibia: Salamandridae): a case study in three Natura 2000 sites in Bulgaria

Borislav Naumov¹, Simeon Lukanov², Emiliya Vacheva³, Maria Naumova⁴,
Deyan Duhlov⁵, Andrey Kolev⁶

- (1) [Corresponding author] Institute of Biodiversity and Ecosystem Research, Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, 2 Yurii Gagarin Street, 1113 Sofia, Bulgaria, herpetologybg@gmail.com
- (2) Institute of Biodiversity and Ecosystem Research, Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, 1 Tsar Osvoboditel Blvd, 1000 Sofia, Bulgaria, simeon_lukanov@abv.bg
- (3) Institute of Biodiversity and Ecosystem Research, Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, 1 Tsar Osvoboditel Blvd, 1000 Sofia, Bulgaria, emilia.vacheva@gmail.com
- (4) Institute of Biodiversity and Ecosystem Research, Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, 1 Tsar Osvoboditel Blvd, 1000 Sofia, Bulgaria, munny@abv.bg
- (5) Independent researcher, Vrabnica 1, Block 538, 1229 Sofia, Bulgaria, deyan_duchalov@abv.bg
- (6) Faculty of Biology, Sofia University “St. Kliment Ohridski”, 8 Dragan Tzankov Blvd, Sofia 1164, Bulgaria, andikolev@gmail.com

Abstract: In Bulgaria, data on the abundance of newt populations are extremely scarce, which greatly complicates their conservation. For most sites of the Natura 2000 network, such data are completely lacking. This paper presents data on the relative abundance of Buresch’s crested newt (*Triturus ivanbureschi*) in three Natura 2000 sites. The data were collected by sampling newts with funnel traps in April and May for two years (2022–2023). The results showed significant variation in newt abundance between ponds and among individual trapping sessions in the same ponds (recorded values ranged between 0.004 and 0.409 adult newts per trapping hour). The representativeness of the collected data, as well as the advantages and disadvantages of the methods used are discussed.

Keywords: Balkan Peninsula, conservation, newt, population estimate

Introduction

Protected areas from the Natura 2000 network play a significant role in the conservation of plant and animal species within the European Union (EEA, 2023). Although nature reserves, national parks and other protected areas have stricter regimes and provide stronger protection for species and habitats, they are relatively small in area. For example in Bulgaria, they cover only 5.27% of the country’s territory, while the Natura 2000 network covers 34.9% (according to official data from the

Environment executive agency and Ministry of environment and water of Bulgaria).

Amphibians are considered the most threatened group of vertebrates globally (Luedtke et al., 2023), which determines the need to implement measures for their conservation. There are 95 amphibian species in Europe (Speybroeck et al., 2020), of which 29 (including all species of newts of the genus *Triturus* Rafinesque, 1815) are listed under Annex II of the Habitats Directive (Council Directive 92/43/EEC), i.e. they are among the target species in the Natura 2000 network. Species conservation in Natura 2000

Fig. 1. Above: Natura 2000 network in Bulgaria with an indication (dark green) of the study sites; below: location of the ponds studied on a relief map with outlines of the corresponding Natura 2000 sites.

sites is normally based on data from scientific research and/or monitoring, but in many cases, there is a complete lack of data regarding population size for many amphibian species. This is especially true for newts, and Buresch's crested newt (*Triturus ivanbureschi*) in particular – although the species is a conservation target in 156 Natura 2000 sites in Bulgaria, data on relative population numbers are available for only 22 of them (see the Information system for protected areas from the ecological network Natura 2000 <https://natura2000.egov.bg/>

[EsriBg.Natura.Public.Web.App](#)). On the other hand, documenting population trends in amphibians is crucial to assessing species status (Crnobrnja-Isailović et al., 2025). In view of this, any scientific data on population size/structure would be of key importance for species conservation at both local and national levels.

The Buresch's crested newt is found in the eastern Balkan Peninsula and northwestern Asia Minor, with the main part of its range falling within Bulgaria (Wielstra et al., 2014). It inhabits a variety of standing

Table 1. Characteristics of the ponds studied: N, E = latitude and longitude in decimal degrees (Datum WGS 1984); Alt. = altitude in metres a.s.l.; Area = water surface area in m² (measured on the national orthophoto 2022 using the corresponding interactive tool: <https://kais.cadastrе.bg/bg/Map>), Dep. = approximate maximum depth of the water body in meters (authors' estimation); Origin = origin of the water body (authors' estimation); Water reg. = water regime i.e. the duration of the presence of water in the pond (permanent – the pond does not dry up; temporary – the pond dries up most summers/autumns); Fish = presence/absence of fish (authors' observations 2022–2023).

Pond ID	N	E	Alt.	Area	Depth	Origin	Water reg.	Fish
V1	42.5141	23.2284	1401	ca. 200	ca. 0.5	Natural	Temporary	no
V2	42.4894	23.2538	1324	ca. 800	ca. 1	Semi-natural	Temporary	no
R1	42.4032	23.3256	921	> 10000*	ca. 0.5	Natural	Temporary	yes
R2	42.3884	23.3653	915	ca. 1450	ca. 1.5	Artificial	Permanent	no
R3	42.4023	23.5248	865	ca. 3100	ca. 1.5	Artificial	Permanent	yes
R4	42.4009	23.5250	864	ca. 50	ca. 1.5	Artificial	Permanent	no
R5	42.4005	23.5259	859	ca. 100	ca. 1.5	Artificial	Permanent	no
P1	42.4687	23.4562	1116	ca. 800	ca. 1	Semi-natural	Temporary	no
P2	42.5357	23.5100	716	ca. 1200	ca. 1	Natural	Permanent	no

* This water body is a seasonal river flood, not visible on orthophoto 2022 (<https://kais.cadastrе.bg/bg/Map>).

water bodies and their surroundings from sea level to about 1350 m a.s.l., and in places even higher (Stojanov et al., 2011). While the distribution of *T. ivanbureschi* is relatively well-studied (Wielstra et al., 2013a, b, 2014), little is known about the population ecology of this species in general. The only scientific studies on this subject concern a single population, located near Sofia, Bulgaria, but outside the Natura 2000 network (see Lukanov & Atanasova, 2025 and references therein).

Here we present data on the relative abundance of *Triturus ivanbureschi* populations in three Natura 2000 sites, obtained by simple methods of capture and individual identification. In the context of amphibian conservation, this paper aims to provide specific examples of newt monitoring, which could be useful in planning conservation activities.

Material and methods

Study area and sampling

The research was conducted in nine ponds (Fig. 1) distributed in three Special Areas of Conservation

(SAC) of the Natura 2000 network in Bulgaria as follows: SAC “BG0000113 Vitosha” – Pond V1 (near Chuyetlovo Village) and Pond V2 (near Yarlovo Village); SAC “BG0000617 Reka Palakaria” – Pond R1 (near Popovyane Village), Pond R2 (near Alino Village), and Ponds R3–R5 (a group of three water bodies near Shiroki Dol Village); SAC “BG0001307 Plana” – Pond P1 (near Plana Village) and Pond P2 (near Dolni Pasarel Village). A detailed description of the ponds studied is given in Table 1 and photos – in Figure 2.

In each pond, newts were sampled four times during the breeding season (April–May in 2022 and 2023) using live traps. We employed rectangular funnel traps (L = 70 cm, H = 25 cm, W = 25 cm; 0.5 cm mesh size; 7 cm funnel opening diameter) with an average exposure time of 17 hours, roughly from sunset to sunrise (for more details on this method see Bock et al., 2009). All captured adult newts were counted, sexed and their ventral side was photographed with a digital camera (for subsequent individual identification), after which they were released into the same pond. Handling of the newts was carried out in accordance with the Bulgarian Ministry of Environment and Water (permit No. 361/13.01.2021).

Fig. 2. The ponds studied (photos were taken by the authors during the fieldwork).

Data processing and analysis

Relative abundance (Ab) was used as an indicator of the abundance of adult newts in the study ponds, calculated by the formula: $Ab = N/(T \cdot H)$, where N is the number of individuals captured, T is the number of traps, and H is the trap exposure time (Tzankov et al., 2014; Naumov et al., 2025).

Individual identification was performed by software-assisted comparison of the ventral patterns of all captured newts from the respective pond. We used the Hotspotter v. 1.0 software (Crall et al., 2013), which has been demonstrated to work well for crested newts and *T. ivanbureschi* in particular (Lukanov & Atanasova, 2025 and references therein). If newt recapture rate was sufficient (i.e., at least 10–20%, see

Kaschube et al., 2022), we used the Jolly–Seber model for open population in order to calculate population size (adults of both sexes in the pond). The model fit was determined by the lowest value for the Akaike’s Information Criterion (AIC) and the model notations were survival rate (Φ), capture probability (p), probability of entrance (b) and population size (N). Population estimates were calculated using the RMark and dplyr libraries in R v. 4.2.1 (R Core Team, 2024).

Results

During the 36 trap sessions, a total of 546 adult individuals of *Triturus ivanbureschi* were caught (396

On the abundance of *Triturus ivanbureschi* Arntzen & Wielstra, 2013: a case study in three Natura 2000 sites in Bulgaria

Table 2. Data for individual trapping sessions per Natura 2000 sites (SAC ID) and ponds (Pond ID): T = number of traps; H = duration of trap exposure (accuracy ½ hour); N = number of (adult) individuals caught; M = number of males caught; F = number of females caught; M(rc) = number of males caught in previous sessions; F(rc) = number of females caught in previous sessions; Ab = relative abundance (calculated as $N/(T*H)$).

SAC ID	Pond ID	Date	T	H	N	M	F	M(rc)	F(rc)	Ab
BG0000113 Vitosha	V1	April 14–15, 2022	10	18	10	5	5	n/a	n/a	0.0556
		May 16–17, 2022	8	18.5	6	3	3	3	2	0.0405
		April 7–8, 2023	10	24.5	4	1	3	—	3	0.0163
		May 10–11, 2023	10	24	5	3	2	2	1	0.0208
	V2	April 6–7, 2022	20	23	84	65	19	n/a	n/a	0.1826
		May 13–14, 2022	17	18	42	27	15	12	—	0.1373
		April 5–6, 2023	20	23.5	86	56	30	8	4	0.1830
		May 3–4, 2023	20	23	77	54	23	19	5	0.1674
BG0000617 Reka Palakaria	R1	April 22–23, 2022	15	15.5	1	1	—	n/a	n/a	0.0043
		May 14–15, 2022	15	15.5	4	2	2	—	n/a	0.0172
		April 11–12, 2023	15	15.5	—	—	—	n/a	n/a	n/a
		May 16–17, 2023	10	14	1	1	—	—	n/a	0.0071
	R2	April 22–23, 2022	15	15	92	76	16	n/a	n/a	0.4089
		May 14–15, 2022	15	14	62	44	18	1	—	0.2952
		April 11–12, 2023	15	15.5	26	20	6	4	—	0.1118
		May 16–17, 2023	10	14	8	7	1	—	1	0.0571
	R3	April 11–12, 2022	10	14.5	—	—	—	n/a	n/a	n/a
		May 11–12, 2022	10	13.5	4	1	3	n/a	n/a	0.0296
		April 7–8, 2023	10	17.5	2	2	—	—	n/a	0.0114
		May 13–14, 2023	10	16	4	4	—	—	n/a	0.0250
	R4	April 11–12, 2022	10	14.5	—	—	—	n/a	n/a	n/a
		May 11–12, 2022	10	14.5	8	6	2	n/a	n/a	0.0552
		April 7–8, 2023	10	15	5	4	1	2*	—	0.0333
		May 13–14, 2023	10	15	5	5	—	3	n/a	0.0333
	R5	April 11–12, 2022	8	14.5	—	—	—	n/a	n/a	n/a
		May 11–12, 2022	10	13.5	17	16	1	n/a	n/a	0.1259
		April 7–8, 2023	10	15.5	17	17	—	7**	n/a	0.1097
		May 13–14, 2023	10	14	6	6	—	4	n/a	0.0429
BG0001307 Plana	P1	April 6–7, 2022	18	24	11	8	3	n/a	n/a	0.0255
		May 13–14, 2022	13	18.5	2	1	1	1	1	0.0083
		April 3–4, 2023	10	17	1	1	—	—	n/a	0.0059
		May 1–2, 2022	10	21.5	—	—	—	n/a	n/a	n/a
	P2	April 19–20, 2022	9	19	25	13	12	n/a	n/a	0.1462
		May 27–28, 2022	10	18	—	—	—	—	—	n/a
		April 3–4, 2023	10	17.5	5	4	1	—	—	0.0286
		May 1–2, 2022	10	21.5	7	7	—	—	—	0.0326

* Incl. one individual initially caught in May 2022 in Pond R5.

** Incl. one individual initially caught in May 2022 in Pond R4.

Table 3. Relative abundance of *Triturus ivanbureschi* in the study ponds (N = number of trap sessions with positive results; Ab = relative abundance calculated).

SAC ID	Pond ID	N	Ab (mean (min–max))
BG0000113 Vitosha	V1	4	0.033 (0.016–0.056)
	V2	4	0.168 (0.137–0.183)
BG0000617 Reka Palakaria	R1	3	0.010 (0.004–0.017)
	R2	4	0.218 (0.057–0.409)
	R3	3	0.022 (0.011–0.030)
	R4	3	0.041 (0.033–0.055)
	R5	3	0.093 (0.043–0.126)
BG0001307 Plana	P1	3	0.013 (0.006–0.026)
	P2	3	0.069 (0.029–0.146)

Table 4. Population estimates for Pond V2 (SAC “BG0000113 Vitosha”), based on CMR data (Phi = survival rate; p = capture probability; b = probability of entrance; N = population size).

Sex	Parameter	Estimate	Standard error	95% confidence interval	
				Lower	Upper
Females	Phi	0.951	0.389	1.37×10^{-6}	1.000
	p	0.088	0.064	0.019	0.317
	b	0.119	0.191	0.004	0.829
	N	322	111	183	647
Males	Phi	0.797	0.130	0.449	0.950
	p	0.214	0.063	0.115	0.363
	b	0.123	0.049	0.054	0.254
	N	381	50	303	502

males and 150 females). The raw data for the individual trap sessions are given in Table 2. The results are described below, separately for each of the three Natura 2000 sites.

In SAC “BG0000113 Vitosha”, the mean relative abundance of newts was 0.100 (0.033 for Pond V1 and 0.168 for Pond V2 respectively; Table 3). In Pond V1, a total of 14 individuals (7 males and 7 females) were captured, with 9 of them recaptured (5 males and 4 females), and in Pond V2, a total of 241 individuals (163 males and 78 females) were captured, with 48 of them recaptured (39 males and 9 females). Sample size and the overall recapture rate of 16.61% allowed for population estimates for Pond V2, and the lowest AIC value (375) was for the model with sex-dependent population parameters (Table 4).

In SAC “BG0000617 Reka Palakaria”, the mean relative abundance of newts was 0.064 (with a variation between 0.010 for Pond R1 and 0.218 for Pond R2; Table 3). In Pond R1, 4 males and 2 females were captured (none of which were recaptured), and in Pond R2, a total of 188 individuals (147 males and 41 females) were captured, but only 6 of them recaptured (5 males and 1 female, i.e. the recapture rate was insufficient for reliable estimates of population parameters). In Pond R3, 7 males and 3 females were captured, but none of which were recaptured. In Pond R4, a total of 14 individuals (11 males and 3 females) were captured, with 4 of them recaptured (only males, including one individual originally recorded in Pond R5), and in Pond R5, a total of 30 individuals (29 males and 1 female) were captured, 11 of which were

recaptured (only males, including one individual originally recorded in Pond R4). The recorded cases of migration were as follows: one of the 6 males captured in 2022 in Pond R4 was captured in 2023 in Pond R5; one of the 16 males captured in 2022 in Pond R5 was captured in 2023 in Pond R4 (the distance between the two ponds is about 80 m).

In SAC “BG0001307 Plana” the mean relative abundance of newts was 0.041 (0.013 for Pond P1 and 0.069 for Pond P2 respectively; Table 3). In Pond P1, a total of 12 individuals (9 males and 3 females) were captured, with 2 of them recaptured (1 male and 1 female), and in Pond P2, a total of 37 individuals (24 males and 13 females) were captured with none of them were recaptured.

Discussion

Our results contribute to knowledge regarding the distribution of *Triturus ivanbureschi* in Bulgaria by establishing new localities within each of the three studied Natura 2000 sites. Regarding the relative abundance of the local populations, our data provide the first such assessment for two of the sites and complement existing data for the third.

SAC “BG0000113 Vitosha”

The presence of *Triturus ivanbureschi* in this SAC is known from literature data, but from other ponds (Buresch & Zonkow, 1941; Stoyneva & Michev, 2007; Tzankov & Stoyanov, 2008; Tzankov et al., 2014). The relative abundance (Ab) from three of these ponds, collected using funnel traps, was estimated as follows: “Dendrariuma: the lower pond” (1190 m a.s.l.) – 0.018, 0.018 and 0.087 (3 trapping sessions); “Dendrariuma: the upper pond” (1200 m a.s.l.) – 0.010 (one trapping session); “Boyana Lake” (1050 m a.s.l.) – 0.005 and 0.010 (2 trapping sessions) (Tzankov et al., 2014). Therefore, on average for these three ponds, we obtain $Ab = 0.025$. On the other hand, the average value for the relative abundance of the species in the ponds from this study is much higher ($Ab = 0.100$). Likely, this difference is due to the ecological characteristics of the ponds, i.e. the water bodies we studied are natural, periodically drying up and do not contain fish, while the water bodies studied by Tzankov et al. were artificial, permanent, and

contained fish. If we derive a general average value (based on the cited results plus the data from this study), we obtain $Ab = 0.063$, which is based on 14 trapping sessions in five ponds located in the northern and southern parts of the SAC. This could be the reference value for the relative abundance of the species in the SAC, because it is based on the same methodology, covers sampling in different parts of the SAC and in different types of water bodies.

There are other ponds in the SAC [visible on satellite images (Google Earth Pro) and/or national orthophoto (<https://kais.cadastrе.bg/bg/Map>)] in which trapping has not been carried out, but were visited by us at least twice in 2010–2024. Two of these are permanent fish ponds (coordinates: N42.4867° E23.2242°, N42.4859° E23.2243°), and another four are decorative ponds that have not been supplied with water for many years (N42.6363° E23.2251°, N42.6435° E23.2587°, N42.6189° E23.2826°, and N42.6207° E23.3040°). The group of eight small water bodies in the central part of the SAC are located at 1930 m a.s.l. (N42.5860° E23.2680°), i.e. above the known vertical distribution limit of *T. ivanbureschi* (up to ca. 1700 m a.s.l. according to Stojanov et al., 2011). Another known pond (at Aleko hut: N42.5736° E 23.3081°, 1720 m a.s.l.), has been visited repeatedly in attempts to catch newts using traps, but in all cases only *Mesotriton alpestris* (Laurenti, 1768) was caught (Tzankov et al., 2014; unpubl. data of the authors from 2015 and 2023–2025). In view of this, it can be assumed that the listed water bodies are not important for the reproduction of *T. ivanbureschi* in the SAC.

Recapture rate was sufficient for estimates of population parameters only in Pond V2, located near the upper limit of the species distribution at 1360 m a.s.l. The only other place with available population data for the species in Bulgaria is also in Vitosha Mts (outside the SAC boundaries), but at an altitude of 800 m a.s.l., near the village of Bistritsa. In a multi-year study, Lukanov & Atanasova (2025) report yearly survivability, probability of capture and population size, which are very similar to the values of the present model for Pond V2 (i.e., for females and males, respectively: $\Phi = 0.831–0.911$ and $0.910–0.941$, $p = 0.061–0.111$ and $0.092–0.311$, $N = 195–259$ and $254–379$). The values for probability of entrance are, however, rather different, as their reported estimates are $b = 0.038–0.051$ and $0.040–0.043$ for females and males, respectively (i.e., the values in this study are

more than double what has been previously reported for both sexes of the species in a pond of similar size). Rather than reflecting a deeper ecological difference between these two ponds, the differences in estimated values for this parameter is more likely due to the limited number of sampling sessions in the present study. We conducted four monthly sessions (April and May in two consecutive years), while for the same years, the Bistritsa site has been sampled weekly for a total of 50 sessions (Lukanov & Atanasova, 2025). Females were less likely to be recaptured than males, which Lukanov & Atanasova (2025) attribute to males having greater vagility and spending more time in the water. The low number of sampling sessions is the likely cause for the large standard errors and the wide confidence intervals for all reported estimates in this study (i.e., the population size interval for females ranges from nearly half to more than double the estimate value, and the standard error is 1/3rd of the estimate). Preliminary exploration of more complex models resulted in unstable estimates and very large uncertainty intervals due to the few sampling sessions and relatively low recapture rates; in addition, *Triturus ivanbureschi* individuals (especially males) may enter or leave breeding ponds during the aquatic season. For these reasons, we retained the simpler POPAN model as an exploratory approach better suited to the structure and limitations of the available data. Our results for this pond strongly indicate a stable population with good male to female ratio, although actual numbers could be lower than the estimates, especially for females.

SAC “BG0000617 Reka Palakaria”

There are no published data on the presence of *Triturus ivanbureschi* in this SAC, but we have detected the species in five water bodies. Other ponds in the SAC, visible on satellite/orthophoto images were not surveyed: the fish farm basins, south of the village of Yarlovo (N42.4502° E23.2816°), the small dams, south of the village of Alino (N42.3796° E23.3867°), etc. Likely, *T. ivanbureschi* occurs in some of these water bodies, but additional research is needed to clarify that. However, the average value derived here ($Ab = 0.064$) could be considered as a reference for the SAC, since it is based on data from five ponds, located in different parts of the SAC, i.e. it probably covers a large part of the variation. Pond R2

had the highest number of captured newts for this SAC (188 individuals), but the recapture rate was still too low for reliable estimates (3.19%). The main reason for this is the large discrepancy in the number of captured newts between the years: 154 in 2022 vs. 34 in 2023. It remains unclear what this difference is due to, as no significant differences were noted between the two years during the fieldwork, either in terms of habitat or weather conditions.

Of special interest are the two cases of male migration in this SAC (see Results), although the distance between Pond R4 and Pond R5 is small (ca. 80 m). A similar phenomenon in *T. ivanbureschi* was recorded by Lukanov (2022) for a larger distance between ponds (ca. 200 m), but also only for males. It is possible that such movements between neighbouring ponds are common in this species, but further studies based on the capture-mark-recapture (CMR) method are needed to clarify this issue.

SAC “BG0001307 Plana”

Triturus ivanbureschi has been reported for one pond – “Bent Dolni Pasarel 1” (Stoyneva & Michev, 2007), and we detected it in two others. It is important to note that the cited locality is a barrage on the Iskar River, hosting various fish species, including predatory ones (see Petkova et al., 2019). Within the SAC there are four more such barrages on the Iskar River (in-between the Iskar Reservoir and Dolni Pasarel Village), in which, we set funnel traps, but detected no newts (authors’ unpublished data from 2011–2012). Therefore, we assume that newt occurrence there may be only sporadic, i.e., these barrages do not play a significant role in the reproduction of newt populations. The only other water bodies visible on satellite/orthophoto images are the two mentioned in this work, which are free of fish. Thus, the $Ab = 0.041$ derived by us could be considered as a reference for the SAC.

Conclusion

The relative abundance of adult *Triturus ivanbureschi* between individual water bodies within Natura 2000 sites varies greatly. Therefore, estimating the Ab for a single pond is not sufficient to derive a reference value for the entire SAC, and further research is needed.

The application of the CMR method undoubtedly gives a much clearer idea of the size of newt populations, but it requires much more effort (more repetitions in the same sites, more manipulations with the newts themselves and subsequent work with specific software), as well as a large number of recaptures, which is far from always possible. In view of this, it is clear that the application of this method even within just one Natura 2000 site would be difficult, and at a regional level – practically impossible. On the other hand, according to the current requirements for periodic reporting under Article 17 of the Habitats Directive, the size of newt populations at the biogeographical region level should be estimated only in the form of the number of individuals (see https://cdr.eionet.europa.eu/help/habitats_art17). As a consequence, there are only two options: to report the population size as unknown (which is exactly the case from a scientific point of view) or – as an intermediate (min-max) number of individuals, which in turn can only be subjective (i.e., a formal estimate without scientific justification). This leads to the following paradox: in both scenarios (unknown or formal number of individuals), population size assessments cannot be used to track any trend, while their purpose is precisely to do so.

In view of the presented results, we recommend that the size of newt populations in Natura 2000 sites (including at the biogeographical level) be estimated on the basis of relative abundance, as an average value from at least four trapping sessions per site, carried out during the breeding season. Although it does not provide information on the absolute abundance of the populations, this method is sufficiently reliable for assessing long-term trends, as long as it is applied regularly and uniformly.

Acknowledgments

We thank Georgi Krastev and Miroslav Slavchev for the field work assistance, as well as the two anonymous reviewers for comments that improved the manuscript.

Conflicts of interest

No potential conflict of interest has been reported by the authors, reviewers, or subject editor.

Author contributions

(using [CrediT](#))

Borislav Naumov: conceptualisation, data curation, formal analysis, investigation, methodology, supervision, validation, visualisation, writing—original draft, writing—review and editing; Simeon Lukanov: data curation, formal analysis, investigation, validation, writing—original draft, writing—review and editing; Emiliya Vacheva: data curation, investigation, validation, writing—original draft, writing—review and editing; Maria Naumova: data curation, investigation, writing—review and editing; Deyan Duhlov: data curation, investigation, writing—review and editing; Andrey Kolev: formal analysis, investigation.

References

- Bock D., Henning V., Steinfartz S. 2009 The use of fish funnel traps for monitoring crested newts (*Triturus cristatus*) according to the Habitats Directive. *Zeitschrift für Feldherpetologie*, Supplement 15: 317–326.
- Buresch I., Zonkow J. 1941 Untersuchungen über die Verbreitung der Reptilien und Amphibien in Bulgarien und auf der Balkanhalbinsel. III. Teil: Schwanzlurche (Amphibia, Caudata). *Mitteilungen aus den Königlichen Naturwissenschaftlichen Instituten in Sofia* 14: 171–273. (In Bulgarian)
- Crall J., Stewart C., Berger-Wolf T., Rubenstein D., Sundaresa S. 2013 Hotspotter – patterned species instance recognition. In: *Proceedings of the 2013 IEEE Workshop on Applications of Computer Vision (WACV 2013)*. Washington, DC: IEEE Computer Society, pp. 230–237. Software available at <http://cs.rpi.edu/hotspotter>.
- Crnobrnja-Isailović J., Schmidt B.R., Denoël M., Ficetola G.F., Cogălniceanu D., Martínez-Solano I., Corti C., Crochet P.-A., Ferri V., Halpern B., Jablonski D., Krása A., Litvinchuk S., Maletzky A., Manenti R., Poboljšaj K., Schulte U., Sotiropoulos K., Speybroeck J., Strachinis I., Romano A., Üzüm N., Wilkinson J., Hobin L., Bellotto V., Clay J., Allen D.J., Trottet A. 2025 Measuring the pulse of European biodiversity. *European Red List of Amphibians*. European Commission, Brussels, 56 pp. <https://doi.org/10.2779/035237>

- EEA 2023 European Environment Agency: Natura 2000 network's contribution to good status. <https://www.eea.europa.eu/en/topics/at-a-glance/nature/state-of-nature-in-europe-a-health-check/natura-2000-networks-contribution-to-good-status>
- Kaschube D.R., Saracco J.F., Ray C., Godwin C.M., Foster K.R., Pyle P. 2022 Minimum capture-recapture rates and years of banding station operations to obtain reliable adult annual survival estimates. *Journal of Field Ornithology* 93 (1): 7. <https://doi.org/10.5751/JFO-00071-930107>
- Luedtke J.A., Chanson J., Neam K., et al. 2023 Ongoing declines for the world's amphibians in the face of emerging threats. *Nature* 622: 308–314. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-023-06578-4>
- Lukanov S. 2022 Inter-pond migration during the aquatic phase by male *Triturus ivanbureschi*. *Russian Journal of Herpetology* 29 (6): 373–376. <https://doi.org/10.30906/1026-2296-2022-29-6-373-376>
- Lukanov S., Atanasova I. 2025 Correlation Between Individual Body Condition and Seasonal Activity in Buresch's Crested Newt, *Triturus ivanbureschi*. *Diversity* 17 (5): 350. <https://doi.org/10.3390/d17050350>
- Naumov B., Lukanov S., Vacheva E., Lazarkevich I., Slavchev M. 2025 Phenology and Sex Ratio of *Triturus cristatus* (Laurenti, 1768) (Amphibia: Salamandridae) at its Southern Range Limit. *Acta Zoologica Bulgarica* 77 (1): 71–84. <https://doi.org/10.71424/azb77.1.002822>
- Petkova S., Kanev E., Dimitrova I., Kisliakov D., Uzunova E. 2019 Fish Pass Functionality in Relation to the Dynamics of Hydrological Conditions in the Upper Course of the River Iskar (Case Study). *Journal of Ecological Engineering* 20 (6): 66–72. <https://doi.org/10.12911/22998993/108918>
- R Core Team 2024 R: A Language and Environment for Statistical Computing. R Foundation for Statistical Computing: Vienna, Austria, 2024. <https://www.R-project.org/> (accessed 20 December 2025).
- Speybroeck J., Beukema W., Dufresnes C., Fritz U., Jablonski D., Lymberakis P., Martínez-Solano I., Razzetti E., Vamberger M., Vences M., Vörös J., Crochet P.-A. 2020 Species list of the European herpetofauna – 2020 update by the Taxonomic Committee of the Societas Europaea Herpetologica. *Amphibia-Reptilia* 41: 139–189. <https://doi.org/10.1163/15685381-bja10010>
- Stojanov A., Tzankov N., Naumov B. 2011 Die Amphibien und Reptilien Bulgariens. Chimaira, Frankfurt am Main, 588 pp.
- Stoyneva M., Michev T. 2007 Database of Bulgarian non-lotic wetlands and their biodiversity. In: Michev T.M., Stoyneva M.P. (eds) Inventory of Bulgarian Wetlands and their Biodiversity. Part 1: Non-Lotic Wetlands, Publ., House Svetlostrouy, Sofia, 364 pp. + CD supplement.
- Tzankov N., Popgeorgiev G., Naumov B., Stoyanov A., Kornilev Y., Petrov B., A. Dyugmedzhiev, Vergilov V., Draganova R., Lukanov S., Westerström A. 2014 Identification guide of the amphibians and reptiles in Vitosha Nature Park. Directorate of Vitosha Nature Park, Sofia, 248 pp. (In Bulgarian)
- Tzankov N., Stoyanov A. 2008 *Triturus cristatus* (Laurenti, 1768): a new species for Bulgaria from its southernmost known localities. *Salamandra* 44 (3): 153–162.
- Wielstra B., Crnobrnja-Isailovic J., Litvinchuk S., Reijnen B., Skidmore A., Sotiropoulos K., Toxopeus A., Tzankov N., Vukov T., Arntzen J. 2013a Tracing glacial refugia of *Triturus* newts based on mitochondrial DNA phylogeography and species distribution modeling. *Frontiers in Zoology* 10: 13.
- Wielstra B., Litvinchuk S., Naumov B., Tzankov N., Arntzen J. 2013b A revised taxonomy of crested newts in the *Triturus karelinii* group (Amphibia: Caudata: Salamandridae), with the description of a new species. *Zootaxa* 3682 (3): 441–453. <https://doi.org/10.11646/zootaxa.3682.3.5>
- Wielstra B., Sillero N., Vörös J., Arntzen J. 2014 The distribution of the crested and marbled newt species (Amphibia: Salamandridae: *Triturus*) – an addition to the New Atlas of Amphibians and Reptiles of Europe. *Amphibia-Reptilia* 35: 376–381. <https://doi.org/10.1163/15685381-00002960>